

Investigation of the Adsorption Efficiency of Methylene Blue Dye in Water Treatment Using Graphene Oxide-Based Adsorbents

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Abstract – Water pollution, particularly the release of industrial dyes into aquatic environments, has become a major environmental problem. Effective and economical treatment methods are needed to reduce this pollution. This study investigates the removal of methylene blue (MB) dye from aqueous solutions by adsorption using graphene oxide (GO). The study consists of three stages. In the first stage, the adsorption performance of GO synthesized by Staudenmaier, Staudenmaier–Hummers, and Hummers methods was compared. 0.1 g of GO was tested with a 300 ppm MB solution at 25 °C and a contact time of 24 hours. GO obtained by the Hummers method exhibited the highest performance with a maximum adsorption capacity of 570 mg/g and a removal efficiency of 95%. In the second stage, the effect of base types (NaOH, NH₄OH, and KOH) on adsorption efficiency was investigated. The best results were obtained using NaOH, with an adsorption capacity of 588 mg/g and a removal efficiency of 98%. In the third stage, the effect of pH was investigated, and the highest efficiency was obtained at pH 9 (466 mg/g capacity, 93.2% removal efficiency). GO samples were characterized by FTIR, zeta potential, and particle size measurements. It was determined that GO obtained by the Hummers method exhibited superior performance due to its high oxidation degree and active adsorption sites. In conclusion, the usability of GO as an effective adsorbent in removing cationic dyes, such as methylene blue, from wastewater was demonstrated. This study shows that graphene oxide has significant potential for environmental water treatment applications.

Keywords – Graphene oxide, Methylene blue, Adsorption, Water pollution, Wastewater treatment

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, the pollution of water resources by various pollutants is considered one of the major environmental problems on a global scale. Among these pollutants, dyes originating from industries such as textiles, plastics, paper, food, leather, and cosmetics play a significant role in polluting aquatic environments [1,2,3]. The textile industry, in particular, stands out as one of the sectors that contributes most to water pollution, second only to agriculture, due to the discharge of large amounts of colored wastewater containing persistent and toxic organic compounds [4,5].

Organic dyes, widely used in these industries, pose a concern due to their high toxicity, low biodegradability, and high chemical and photochemical stability [6,7]. The release of these substances

into the environment not only leads to the deterioration of water quality but also has negative effects on aquatic organisms and human health [8,9]. In this context, dyes such as methylene blue (MB), frequently used in the textile industry, are noteworthy for their synthetic and cationic structures with high solubility in water and alcohol. The chemical structure of methylene blue is defined as 3,7-bis(dimethylamino)phenazathionium chloride ($C_{16}H_{18}ClN_3S \cdot H_2O$, $M = 319.86 \text{ g} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$). Due to its stable heteropolyaromatic structure, methylene blue is challenging in terms of biodegradability and exhibits high resistance to conventional treatment methods, increasing its persistence in aquatic environments [10,11,12].

Fig. 1 Chemical structure of methylene blue [2]

Various treatment methods have been developed to reduce the environmental impact of pollutants such as methylene blue. Among these methods, adsorption stands out for its ease of application and high efficiency. Several physicochemical and biological methods, including photocatalytic degradation, oxidation, reduction, electrochemical degradation, and adsorption, have been considered for dye removal [13,14]. However, adsorption is both highly effective and widely used due to its low cost, high efficiency, and the possibility to regenerate and reuse adsorbents [15]. Adsorption produces fewer secondary byproducts, offering a significant advantage over other treatments [16]. Many studies have aimed to develop high-performance adsorbents for removing organic pollutants from wastewater [17,18]. Carbon-based materials especially activated carbon, graphene, mesoporous carbon, carbon nanotubes, and carbon aerogels are prominent in these studies [19]. Recently, graphene oxide (GO) has drawn great interest as a carbon-based material thanks to its exceptional physicochemical properties. GO is a two-dimensional nanomaterial with a heterogeneous surface rich in oxygen-containing functional groups, such as hydroxyl, carboxyl, and epoxide [20]. This functionalization gives GO both hydrophilic and hydrophobic traits, allowing interaction with a wide range of pollutants. As a result, GO can interact with organic and inorganic molecules through hydrogen bonding, electrostatic interactions, π - π stacking, Van der Waals forces, and hydrophobic interactions. Despite its superior adsorption performance, GO has some limitations, such as difficulty in solid/liquid separation after purification [21,22].

The superior adsorption properties of graphene oxide (GO) and other carbon-based materials give them great potential in water treatment applications. This study aims to increase the effectiveness of GO in the adsorption of methylene blue dye by investigating the effects of different synthesis methods and adsorption parameters. Numerous studies in the literature have shown that GO is effective in removing various ionic dyes such as Rhodamine B, Acid Orange 8 (AO8), Direct Red 23, crystal violet, malachite green, proflavin, and eosin B from aqueous media [23,24,25,26,27]. Accordingly, in the present study, the adsorption performances of GO forms obtained by three different synthesis methods—Staudenmaier, Staudenmaier–Hummers, and Hummers in aqueous solutions containing methylene blue were comparatively investigated. Furthermore, the effects of various operating parameters such as pH (2, 5, and 9) and the type of base used (NaOH, KOH, and NH_4OH) on the adsorption process were evaluated. The results obtained are expected to provide a scientific contribution to a better understanding of the potential of graphene oxide as an adsorbent in water treatment. Finally, the characterization of the synthesized materials was carried out using various analytical techniques such as FTIR spectroscopy, zeta potential and particle size measurements, UV-visible spectroscopy, and electrical conductivity measurements.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The chemicals used in this study were pure graphite, hydrochloric acid (HCl), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), potassium permanganate (KMnO₄), potassium chlorate (KClO₃), sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), phosphoric acid (H₃PO₄), nitric acid (HNO₃), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), potassium hydroxide (KOH), ammonium hydroxide (NH₄OH), and methylene blue. These chemicals were obtained from Merck and Sigma-Aldrich. The equipment used in the experiments was an IKA C-MAG HS10 magnetic stirrer, a Beckman Coulter Allegra X-12R centrifuge, a Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer, a Bruker Tensor 2 FTIR, and a Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS instrument. pH measurements were performed using a HANNA Edge pH meter; The characterization of graphene oxide was performed using UV-visible spectroscopy, FTIR analysis, zeta potential, and particle size distribution.

2.1 Synthesis of Graphene Oxide

Graphene oxide was synthesized using pure graphite by three different methods: Staudenmaier, Staudenmaier–Hummers, and Hummers. Experimental procedures were carried out by varying the concentrations of the reactants used. In the first step, graphite was added to a reactor consisting of a mixture of nitric acid and sulfuric acid. The temperature of the reaction medium was kept constant at 5 °C [28,33], and potassium chlorate was added slowly under mechanical stirring. The mixture was stirred at 520 rpm at 5 °C for 24 hours. Then, the reaction temperature was increased to 95 °C, and the stirring process was continued for an additional 6 hours with the addition of distilled water [29,31]. Hydrochloric acid was added to remove metal ions and residual impurities, and hydrogen peroxide was used to neutralize the oxidizing agents and terminate the reaction. The resulting product was washed and purified by precipitation with distilled water until the pH value reached the range of 3-4. Finally, graphene oxide was centrifuged at 3750 rpm for 5 minutes and dried in an oven at 65 °C [30,32].

2.2 Adsorption Experiments

The adsorption of methylene blue on graphene oxide (GO) was investigated in three separate experimental series to evaluate the effect of different parameters on the adsorption process. These experiments aimed to determine the effect of the GO synthesis method on the adsorption capacity of methylene blue, the effect of the type of base used on dye adsorption, and the effect of solution pH on adsorption efficiency.

First Stage: In this stage, the effect of GO synthesis methods on the adsorption capacity was evaluated. 0.1 g of GO synthesized by Staudenmaier, Staudenmaier–Hummers, and Hummers methods was mixed with 100 mL of methylene blue solution at a concentration of 300 ppm. The samples were stirred for 24 hours at 25°C and then centrifuged for 5 minutes at 3750 rpm. The amount of remaining methylene blue was measured at 664 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer, and the adsorption efficiency was calculated based on the rate of decrease in absorbance value. The obtained solid samples were dried in an oven at 65 °C to remove residual water.

Second Stage: In this stage, the effect of base types on adsorption efficiency was investigated. 0.05 g of GO synthesized by the Hummers method was added to a 300 ppm methylene blue solution. The pH of the solutions was adjusted to 10 using NaOH, KOH, and NH₄OH, respectively. After the mixtures were left to stand for 24 hours at 25 °C, they were centrifuged, and the resulting supernatants were analyzed using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The obtained solid samples were dried in an oven at 65 °C to remove residual water.

Third Stage: In the final stage, the effect of the pH value of the solution on the adsorption capacity was investigated. 0.05 g of GO synthesized by the Hummers method was mixed with a 250 ppm methylene blue solution. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 2, 5, and 9 using NaOH and HCl, respectively. After mixing the mixtures at 25°C for 24 hours, they were centrifuged, and the remaining dye concentration was measured with a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The obtained solid samples were dried in an oven at 65 °C to remove residual water.

2.3 Analysis

Adsorption performances were evaluated based on the dye removal percentage and the amount adsorbed under equilibrium conditions, and these values were calculated using the equations given below.

$$\%R = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$q_e(\text{mg/g}) = (C_0 - C_e) \times \frac{V}{W} \quad (2)$$

Where %R is the dye removal percentage, C_0 (mg/L) represents the initial dye concentration, C_e (mg/L) represents the equilibrium concentration of the dye solution, W (g) represents the mass of the adsorbent, and V (L) represents the volume of the dye solution.

Calibration Curve – Methylene Blue

In order to create the calibration curve, methylene blue solutions with concentrations ranging from 5–500 ppm were prepared. Absorbance measurements were performed using a UV–Visible spectrophotometer at a maximum absorption wavelength of 664 nm. The resulting calibration curve is presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Calibration curve for methylene blue solutions prepared at different concentrations

Following adsorption experiments, various characterization analyses were performed to evaluate the structural properties and surface morphologies of the samples. Using FTIR spectroscopy, the major functional groups on the graphene oxide (GO) surface, particularly hydroxyl, carboxyl, and epoxide groups, were identified. Zeta potential measurements were performed to determine the surface charge of the particles in the GO suspension and to assess their colloidal stability. Particle size distribution (zeta size) measurements determined the particle size of GO, thus providing information about the distribution of GO layers in aqueous medium. Additionally, absorbance measurements were performed using UV-visible spectrophotometry to determine the optical properties of the samples, and electrical conductivity was measured using a conductivity meter. The obtained data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Characterization parameters of graphene oxide used in methylene blue adsorption

Quality Criteria	Symbol	Explanation	Information	Target for GO
1	ZP	Zeta Potential	Colloidal stability and dispersion status	The best with the highest absolute value.
2	PB	Particle size	Nanostructural properties and distribution	The smallest particle size is best.
3	FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy	Identification of functional groups on the surface	Spectrum interpretation
4	UV-vis	UV-Visible Spectrophotometer	Determining the amount of dye adsorbed	Highest absorbance
5	EC	Electrical conductivity	Electron conductivity and structural characteristics	Suitable conductivity value

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study investigates the effects of graphene oxide, obtained by different synthesis methods, on the adsorption capacity of methylene blue dye. In this context, the effects of the graphene oxide synthesis method, the type of base used, and the pH value on the adsorption performance were evaluated in detail. The dye removal rates and adsorption efficiencies obtained under experimental conditions are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Methylene Blue removal results under different experimental conditions

Experiment Feature	C _o	C _e	The amount of adsorbent Methylene Blue	mg Methylene Blue/mgGO	% Methylene Blue Adsorption Efficiency
GO-MB-ST	300	144	156	312	52
GO-MB-ST-H	300	76	224	448	74,7
GO-MB-H	300	15	285	570	95
GO-MB-KOH	300	15	285	570	95
GO-MB-NaOH	300	6	294	588	98
GO-MB-NH ₄ OH	300	8	292	584	97,3
GO-MB-pH2	250	109	141	282	56,4
GO-MB-pH5	250	43	207	414	82,8
GO-MB-pH9	250	17	233	466	93,2

$$\%MB = (\text{Absorbed MB}/C_o) * 100 = (156/300) * 100 = 52\%$$

Table 3 presents the solution conductivity values ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) of graphene oxide (GO) samples after adsorption under different experimental conditions. According to these data, the conductivity of GO samples varies depending on the synthesis method, the type of base used, and the pH conditions. The higher conductivity values obtained in the GO sample synthesized by the Hummers method can be attributed to the increase in the ionizable oxygen functional groups on the surface and the amount of free ions in the solution. The change in conductivity depending on the base type is due to the electrical transport properties of Na^+ , K^+ , and NH_4^+ ions present in the solution. The high conductivity observed at pH 2 (1.95 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) can be explained by the increasing ion concentration in the acidic environment, while the decrease observed at pH 9 is associated with a decrease in ionic mobility. These results show that the ionic structure of the solution plays a decisive role in the surface charge, colloidal stability, and adsorption behavior of GO.

Table 3. Solution conductivity values ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) of GO samples after adsorption under different experimental conditions

Experiment Feature	Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)
GO-MB-ST	1,12
GO-MB-ST-H	1,39
GO-MB-H	1,32
GO-MB-KOH	1,09
GO-MB-NaOH	1,10
GO-MB-NH ₄ OH	1,19
GO-MB-pH2	1,95
GO-MB-pH5	1,19
GO-MB-pH9	1,05

3.1 Effect of Synthesis Method on Methylene Blue Adsorption Capacity

The effect of graphene oxide on methylene blue adsorption was systematically compared among samples synthesized by Staudenmaier, Staudenmaier–Hummers, and Hummers methods. The results presented in Table 2 show that the adsorption performance is strongly dependent on the synthesis method.

Under conditions where the initial MB concentration is 300 ppm, GO synthesized by the Staudenmaier method showed the lowest adsorption performance; the equilibrium concentration (C_e) was determined to be 144 ppm, the adsorption capacity 312 mg/g, and the removal efficiency 52%. This relatively low performance can be attributed to the low oxidation degree of graphene and, consequently, the limited number of oxygenated functional groups on the surface. In contrast, GO obtained by the Staudenmaier–Hummers method showed a higher adsorption performance. In this example, while the MB concentration was reduced to 76 ppm, the adsorption capacity was determined to be 448 mg/g, and the removal efficiency was 74.7%. This improvement can be explained by the further oxidation of the graphite layers and the increased formation of hydroxyl, carboxyl, and epoxide groups. The highest adsorption performance was obtained for GO synthesized by the Hummers method. Under the same experimental conditions, the MB concentration was reduced to 15 ppm, the adsorption capacity was determined to be 570 mg/g, and the removal efficiency was 95%. These results show that the Hummers method is the most effective method for producing highly oxidized GO with a high specific surface area and dense active adsorption sites. These data are presented in Figure 9.

Fig. 3. Effects of graphene oxide synthesis methods on methylene blue adsorption.

The FTIR analysis results in Figure 4 clearly reveal the presence of oxygen-containing functional groups in the synthesized graphene oxide (GO) samples. These include hydroxyl ($\approx 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$), carbonyl ($\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\approx 1720\text{ cm}^{-1}$), and epoxy/alkoxy ($\text{C}-\text{O}$, $1220\text{--}1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$) groups. Observed changes in intensity and small wavenumber shifts, particularly in the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $\text{C}=\text{C}$ bands after methylene blue adsorption, indicate strong interactions between the dye molecules and the GO surface. More pronounced band changes in the GO-MB-H sample show that GO synthesized by the Hummers method has a higher oxidation state. This suggests there are more active adsorption sites on the surface. In conclusion, FTIR analyses confirm that methylene blue is successfully adsorbed onto the GO surface via electrostatic interactions and π - π coupling.

Fig. 4. FTIR analysis results of graphene oxide synthesis methods

The Zeta potential results shown in Figure 5 reveal that the surface charge of graphene oxide is significantly dependent on the synthesis method. The most negative value (-41.7 mV) was obtained in the sample synthesized by the Hummers method; this value is lower when compared to the samples produced by the Staudenmaier (-25.7 mV) and Staudenmaier–Hummers (-40.7 mV) methods. The more negative surface charge indicates the presence of higher amounts of functional groups containing ionizable oxygen, such as carboxyl and hydroxyl groups, which increases colloidal stability and strengthens the electrostatic attraction with methylene blue, which exhibits cationic properties. Furthermore, it was observed that the hydrodynamic particle size of GO also varies significantly depending on the synthesis method. It was determined that the sample obtained by the Hummers method had the smallest particle size (210.9 nm), whereas the Staudenmaier (269 nm) and Staudenmaier–Hummers (275.6 nm) methods resulted in larger particle sizes. This size reduction can be explained by the higher degree of oxidation and more effective exfoliation of the graphene layers, indicating improved colloidal dispersion. The smaller particle size contributes to the strengthening of electrostatic and π – π interactions with methylene blue molecules by providing a higher accessible surface area.

Fig. 5 Zeta potential and particle size results regarding the effects of graphene oxide synthesis methods on methylene blue adsorption

3.2. Effect of Base Type on Methylene Blue Adsorption

The effect of base type on MB adsorption was investigated using KOH, NaOH, and NH₄OH for an initial concentration of 300 ppm. The results show a gradual increase in adsorption performance depending on the base type used. With the use of KOH, the adsorption capacity was determined to be 570 mg/g, the residual concentration 15 ppm, and the removal efficiency 95%. In the presence of NH₄OH, adsorption further increased, the residual concentration decreased to 8 ppm, the adsorption capacity increased to 584 mg/g, and the removal efficiency increased to 97.3%. The highest performance was obtained when using NaOH; in this case, the residual concentration was only 6 ppm, the adsorption capacity was 588 mg/g, and the removal efficiency was 98% (Table 2). This trend can be explained by the increase in negative charge density on the GO surface due to the deprotonation of functional groups on the surface under basic conditions. The increased negative charge density strengthens the electrostatic interactions between the negatively charged GO surface and cationic MB molecules, contributing to an increase in adsorption capacity.

Fig. 6. Effects of base type on methylene blue adsorption

The FTIR analyses shown in Figure 7 demonstrate that significant changes occur in the functional groups on the GO surface after adsorption with different base types. In particular, the observed decrease in the intensity of the –OH stretching vibrations around 3400 cm⁻¹ and the C=O bands in the 1720 cm⁻¹ region confirms the binding of methylene blue molecules to the GO surface. Changes in aromatic C=C vibrations in the 1600–1500 cm⁻¹ range in samples treated with NaOH, KOH, and NH₄OH indicate the formation of π - π interactions with dye molecules. The more pronounced band changes in the sample treated with KOH suggest stronger surface interactions. These results reveal that the base type plays a significant role in the adsorption mechanism by influencing the GO surface chemistry.

Fig. 7 FTIR analysis results of the base type

The zeta potential results in Figure 8 varied depending on the type of base used. Compared to NaOH (–36.7mV), KOH (–36mV), and NH₄OH (–33mV), NaOH provided the most negative surface charge. This can be explained by the effects of different cations on the electrical double-layer structure and the

changes in the degree of deprotonation of the functional groups on the GO surface. The higher negative surface charge improves dispersion and reduces the tendency for aggregation due to increased electrostatic repulsion between particles. Similarly, it was observed that the type of base used significantly affected the hydrodynamic particle size of GO, with the smallest particle size (211.5 nm) obtained using NaOH and the largest size (236 nm) using KOH. These differences are related to the cations altering the double-layer thickness and particle stability in the colloidal system. In conclusion, the type of base not only regulates the pH of the solution but also stands out as an important parameter affecting the dispersion behavior of GO and, consequently, its adsorption performance.

Fig. 8 Zeta potential and particle size results regarding the effects of base type on methylene blue adsorption

3.3. Effect of pH on Methylene Blue Adsorption

The effect of solution pH on methylene blue (MB) adsorption was investigated in the pH range of 2–9 for an initial concentration of 250 ppm. The results show that adsorption performance is strongly dependent on pH. At pH 2, the adsorption performance is relatively low, with a removal efficiency of 56.4% and an adsorption capacity of 282 mg/g. This low performance can be explained by the weakening of electrostatic interactions due to the protonation of functional groups on the graphene oxide (GO) surface in an acidic environment. When the pH was increased to 5, a significant increase in adsorption performance was observed, with an adsorption capacity of 414 mg/g and a removal efficiency of 82.8%. Under pH 9 conditions, adsorption reached its maximum level; the adsorption capacity was determined to be 466 mg/g and the removal efficiency 93.2% (Figure 9). These findings reveal that basic conditions

strongly support methylene blue adsorption, and that this is due to increased electrostatic and π - π interactions with the negative charging of the GO surface.

Fig. 9 Effect of pH on methylene blue adsorption

The FTIR analysis results in Figure 10 reveal that the adsorption process performed under different pH conditions affects the structure of functional groups on the GO surface. In particular, the observed changes in the intensity of the -OH band around 3400 cm^{-1} and the C=O band around 1720 cm^{-1} with increasing pH indicate that the interactions between methylene blue molecules and the GO surface are strengthened. The more pronounced band shifts in an alkaline environment suggest an increase in the active sites on the surface due to the deprotonation of carboxylic groups. At pH 9, changes in aromatic C=C vibrations confirm that π - π interactions with dye molecules occur more effectively. These results demonstrate that high pH values optimize the GO surface chemistry and significantly improve the adsorption mechanism.

Fig. 10 Effects of pH experiment on FTIR results

Figure 11 shows that with increasing pH, the surface charge of GO becomes more negative, and its zeta potential decreases from -35.3 mV at pH 2 to -40.6 mV at pH 9. Deprotonation of carboxylic groups in alkaline medium increases the negative charge density on the surface, strengthening the electrostatic repulsion between particles and improving colloidal stability. In parallel, increasing pH also reduces the hydrodynamic particle size of GO, decreasing from 267.8 nm at pH 2 to 238.9 nm at pH 9. This can be explained by reduced interlayer aggregation and improved dispersion. The better dispersion and increased negative surface charge obtained under high pH conditions increase the accessibility of active adsorption sites, contributing to stronger electrostatic interactions with cationic methylene blue.

Fig. 11 Zeta potential and particle size results regarding the effects of pH on methylene blue adsorption

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, the methylene blue adsorption performance of graphene oxide under different synthesis methods, basic modification, and pH parameters was comprehensively evaluated. Experimental results revealed that the synthesis method plays a decisive role in the surface properties, particle size distribution, and surface charge of graphene oxide. Comparative analyses showed that graphene oxide synthesized by the Hummers method had a higher oxidation degree, more active adsorption sites, and improved surface functional groups, which was confirmed by its superior adsorption performance. Graphene oxide obtained by the Hummers method exhibited the highest performance with a maximum adsorption capacity of 570 mg/g and a removal efficiency of 95%.

When the effect of the base type was examined, it was observed that basic treatment with NaOH increased the surface charge, strengthening the electrostatic attraction and raising the adsorption capacity to 588 mg/g. In addition, it was determined that the pH value of the solution is an important parameter in the adsorption mechanism, and maximum adsorption efficiency was achieved under pH 9 conditions. Zeta potential and particle size analyses showed that a high negative surface charge and a suitable particle size distribution increased the adsorption efficiency.

Consequently, the findings reveal that graphene oxide synthesized by the Hummers method and modified with a suitable basic process is a high-performance adsorbent with significant environmental

applications for the removal of cationic dyes from wastewater. Overall, it is confirmed that optimizing the synthesis parameters and experimental conditions significantly increases the effectiveness of graphene oxide as a promising adsorbent in the treatment of water contaminated with organic dyes.

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